

Supplementary Materials for CHyMER

I. GENERIC HYPOTHESES

In Table I, we provide the generic hypotheses from Harkous et al. [1]. Below, we have provided the heuristics used in [1] to sample potential privacy reviews.

- A review i is labeled as *maybe-privacy* (potential privacy reviews) if $N_E(i, 0.8) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.7) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.6) \geq 5$ or $N_E(i, 0.5) \geq 7$.
- A review i is labeled as *maybe-not-privacy* if $N_E(i, 0.4) = 0$.
- Rest of the reviews are labeled as *undetermined*.

II. EXAMPLES OF FALSE POSITIVES

Below we show some examples of reviews that were identified as FP in NLI with domain-specific hypotheses and their corresponding heuristics.

Example 1:

One needs to take photo of social security card to finish establishing account, and without the card you can't proceed, even though you provided the ssn in an earlier window, dob, address and email. no alternative is offered. poor set-up.

Corresponding hypotheses: "The app collects more financial data than necessary" and "The user is concerned about how the app harvests their financial data."

We can notice that even though the user mentioned various financial details, including social security number and social security card, the review is not related to privacy or security issues, but it discusses about the problem with the account setup functionality and asks for an alternative to uploading a social security card.

Example 2:

I linked my bank account through the login process provided by the app. the link was successful and the app said i was able to instantly start trading using my deposits. i did a few deposits of a small amount to get used to the trading aspect. a few days later, i get an email and notification through the app that all my transfers got returned because the bank account i linked didn't exist. what?? i literally linked it using my bank login and got the confirmation! then what's worse, is they charge you a \$30 fee for the fees that get reversed! it would make sense if the fee was added for a legitimate reason, but this wasn't my fault, i did everything they asked me to do. support still hasn't reached back out to me either after 5

TABLE I
GENERIC PRIVACY CONCEPTS AND ASSOCIATED HYPOTHESES FROM [1]

Privacy Concept	Hypotheses
Concepts from Solove's Taxonomy [2]	
Surveillance	1. The user is facing a data surveillance issue.
Interrogation	2. The user is forced to provide information.
Aggregation	3. Personal user information is collected from other sources.
Insecurity	4. The user is concerned about protecting their personal data.
Identification	5. A data anonymity topic is discussed.
Secondary Use	6. The user is concerned about the purposes of personal data access.
Exclusion	7. The user wants to correct their personal information.
Breach of Confidentiality	8. A breach of data confidentiality is discussed.
Disclosure	9. Personal data disclosure is discussed.
Exposure	10. The app exposes a private aspect of the user life.
Increased Accessibility	11. User's data has been made accessible to public.
Blackmail	12. A data blackmailing issue is discussed.
Appropriation	13. User data is being exploited for other purposes.
Distortion	14. False data is presented about the user.
Intrusion	15. Unwanted intrusion to personal info is discussed.
Decisional Interference	16. Intrusion by the government to the user's life is discussed.
Concepts from Wang and Kobsa's Taxonomy [3]	
Notice/Awareness	17. Opting out from personal data collection is discussed.
	18. More access than needed is required.
Data Minimization	
Purpose Specification	19. The reason for data access is not provided.
Collection Limitation	20. Too much personal data is collected.
Use Limitation	21. The data is being used for unexpected purposes.
Onward Transfer	22. Data sharing with third parties is discussed.
Choice/Consent	23. User choice for personal data collection is discussed.
	24. User did not allow access to their personal data.
Generic Privacy Concepts	
Generic Privacy Issues	25. A data privacy topic is discussed.
	26. Protecting user's personal data is discussed.
	27. This is about a privacy feature.
	28. The user is facing a privacy issue.
Positive Privacy Issues	29. The user likes that data privacy is provided.
	30. The user wants privacy.
	31. The app has privacy features.

days, so needless to say unless it's fixed i won't be using this app any longer.

Corresponding hypotheses: "The app collects more financial data than necessary" and "Unauthorized bank transfers are performed."

We can notice that the user is mentioning about providing bank login details to link the account and about the transaction. However, it is not related to any privacy or security concerns, as the user is complaining about an issue with the

TABLE II
EXAMPLES OF PSRS EXTRACTED USING CHYMER.

App	Date	Privacy Review
ETrade	07/04/2013	Check the permissions this app takes, specifically "Hardware controls". It records audio and video without your confirmation. Seems more like a corporate espionage or insider trading spy tool than a trading app with this type of capability. No thank you, I'll try another app and company.
ETrade	26/01/2016	Why do you need so much permission for mobile trading application? Why do you need my phone log? Would someone check if this is a Spyware? I would love to hear explanation from the creator of this application.
Fidelity	08/10/2020	Asks for void checks and so much more to access my bank account.
Fidelity	20/07/2014	As an Android developer and Fidelity customer, I'm disappointed in this app. It overall looks good with good functionality, but has several serious deficiencies. Security: It allows your user ID to be typed in using whatever soft keyboard you have installed. Many of these keyboards store their memory list on "disk" (flash) or even upload them to servers. This means that your user ID (and maybe password, not sure) are at their mercy. There are ways in Android to avoid this vulnerability (specify your own input method) and they should be using them! I have reported this to Fidelity several times, with no interest on their part.
Personal Capital	05/02/2014	They knew; 1) my total asset worth 2) which institutions (banks and brokerages) I use and 3) asset allocations of my portfolio. Not feeling too secure.
Personal Capital	30/04/2021	They want you to link all your bank accounts and give them the bank account numbers and passwords and won't let you skip this. Deleted app before risking my bank account being drained and identity being stolen.
Robinhood	01/09/2020	I had 5 different transactions totaling \$10,800 trying to be removed from my account by Robinhood. Currently trying to work on figuring this out, but their system is clearly not secure with your bank information.
Robinhood	28/01/2021	Day one of downloading the application I received a notification that my account was accessed from a phone in AZ. I removed the phone and changed my password as instructed by Robinhood. A couple hours later the phone accessing my account from AZ appeared once again. Don't trust the security on this app!!!
Schwab	14/12/2017	As soon as you download the app and enter your info they hit your credit. No where in the legal disclosure or terms and condition does it say anything about your FICO scores, credit checks, etc.
Schwab	05/10/2019	Serious question to Charles Schwab: why in the world does your app need access to my device's Bluetooth? That means that this app has been surreptitiously been accessing Bluetooth all along, and now with iOS 13 the user is finally made aware and given a choice to disallow it. I expect this type of thing from shady ad targeting businesses masquerading as games and such, not from a financial institution that I am to trust my personal and financial information with. This deserves more than a full explanation- it deserves an APOLOGY and removal of such underhanded background activity. One star.
Stash	01/04/2021	Someone hacked into my account, changed my email and password, and transferred my available funds to their account. When I saw the notifications, I contacted stash after not being able to login to my account. They told me there was nothing they could do to and that someone would contact me in a few business days. In the meantime, the transfer of all my money went through. No one will save your money from being taken. Do not put yourself at risk on this app, they are not safe.
Stash	19/12/2017	Needs your social security number...nope not going to happen, I don't feel like having my identity stolen...FAIL
TD Ameritrade	16/02/2018	The App sometimes (not always) does NOT automatically log you out after even many hours of non-activity. Please fix this major security risk! Please provide an option to automatically log out after, say, 10 minutes of inactivity.
TD Ameritrade	19/11/2019	Started to get bogus calls after providing their company with my vital information. I don't have the means to prove anything. What I am saying is if you're not in a position to fight stuff like this you may need to think twice before installing this.

Fig. 2. Top 50 bigrams from PSRs that are extracted using CHyMER. The most frequent privacy and security issues are related to financial data selling and account hacking.